

Implemented Crime Prevention Strategies of PNP in Salug Valley, Zamboanga Del Sur, Philippines

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Abstract – *This study aimed primarily to determine the effectiveness of crime prevention strategies implemented by the Salug Valley Philippine National Police (PNP) in terms of Police Integrated Patrol System, Barangay Peacekeeping Operation, Anti-Criminality Operation, Integrated Area Community Public Safety services, Bantay Turista and School Safety Project as evaluated by 120 inhabitants and 138 PNP officers from four Municipalities of Salug Valley Zamboanga del Sur. Stratified random sampling was utilized in determining the respondents. Index crime rate were correlated with the crime prevention strategies of the PNP in town of Salug Valley.*

A descriptive method of research was applied in this study utilizing self-made questionnaire. The data collected were analyzed using the main statistical tools like frequency count, percentage, mean computation, Kruskal Wallis Analysis of Variance and simple correlation.

Findings of the study revealed that the crime prevention strategies in four (4) municipalities were “much effective” to include Integrated Patrol System, Barangay Peace Keeping Operations, Anti-Criminality Operations, Integrated Area Community Public Safety Services, Bantay Turista and School Safety Project in connection to the responses of 158 participants.

There is a significant relationship between crime prevention strategies employed and index crime rate.

Keywords – *Crime Prevention, Preventing Crimes, Effectiveness of Strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Community Safekeeping has been defined as the objective to safeguard the vital core of human lives and properties from critical ubiquitous threats, in a way that is consistent with long term fulfillment [1]. With this notion, the Philippine National Police as the frontline of criminal justice system in enforcement of law were accustomed on protection of life and property of the public.

Crime is a significant concern in urban areas of the Philippines. Typical criminal acts include pick-pocketing, confidence schemes, acquaintance scams, and, in some cases, credit card fraud. Carjacking, kidnappings, robberies, and violent assaults sporadically occur. According to the Philippine National Police Directorate for Investigation and Detective Management, the Total Crime Volume (TCV) in 2012 was 217,812 as compared to 2011 with 241,988 – a decrease of 24,176. Of the total 217,812 crime incidents, the National Capital Regional Police Office (NCRPO) registered the highest with 56,978 followed by Regions 3 (Bulacan, Bataan, Pampanga,

Nueva Ecija, Zambales, Tarlac, Aurora) and 7 (Cebu, Bohol, Negros Oriental, Siquijor) with 22,498 and 20,466 reported incidents respectively. Theft (43,606 incidents), physical assault (34,825 incidents), and robbery (26,988 incidents) are the top three commonly committed crimes according to the TCV [2].

Crimes involving theft, physical assault, and robbery were the top three most common crimes reported to local authorities in 2013. Typical criminal acts include: pickpocketing, confidence schemes, acquaintance scams, and credit card fraud [3].

It is essential that the police should shift its mindset from its traditional policing function of law enforcement to a more substantial role of being law enforcer and community leader. The police should go beyond the scope of their traditional duties and become increasingly conscious of the role they can play in the solution of the major problems of society, with particular reference to those raised by the potential threat brought about by the escalation of

crime. The police should not merely be instruments of crime control or suppression [4].

Similarly the mandate of the PNP is pointed towards peace and order, ensuring public safety and further strengthening capacity of local government in the effective administration and delivery of the basic services to the citizenry through the establishment of a highly efficient and competent police force [5].

Equally, Republic Act No. 8551 mandated the Philippine National Police (PNP) as a service provider for the preservation of peace and safety of the community. The PNP shall be so organized to ensure accountability and uprightness in police exercise of discretion as well as to achieve efficiency and effectiveness of its members and units in the performance of their functions [6].

Taking into account the unfortunate events in MAMASAPANO in the 25th of January 2015 and the controversies involved by officials in the government in this country have resulted a stronger commitment by all concerned to devote effort and time to essential task of seeking peace and order.

Indeed, the Philippine National Police today is challenged by time in terms of the effectiveness of the institution in maintaining a peaceful and orderly society as well as its efficiency and effectiveness in deterring criminal activities and preventing the successful commission of crimes. Such can be measured through the crime statistics recorded in the police station.

The incidence on August 03, 2012 raised situational concerns among PNP officers and government agencies when a Barangay (village) Captain together with the member of a private armed group was neutralized and arrested carry explosives and firearms in Barangay Lourmah, Mahayag, Zamboanga del Sur[7].

In addition, the report of [8] attack and burning of poultry farm owned by Onyx Go on October 28, 2012 which was perpetuated due to the refusal to give extortion money by seven members of the New People's Army inflicting great loses amounting to 3.5 to 4 million pesos raised greater concern and worries among members of the business sector.

Salug Valley remains as the center of business and trade in the eastern part of Zamboanga del Sur and it is advancing towards turning into the most dynamic region of the territory in terms of doing much for its blasting industry [9].

With this background at hand, the researcher ventured to investigate in the four municipal police

stations in Salug Valley. It is a challenging duty for the PNP in their capacity as enforcers of the law in their respective area of responsibility to keep the area safe to attract more investors and to make sure that people are safe and secure in the community. To wit, this study will assess the effect of their endeavors in the implemented crime prevention and suppression efforts in crime rate reduction as basis for future intervention programs.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aims to look into whether the police personnel in the Municipal Police Stations in Salug Valley, namely: Dumingag, Mahayag, Molave and Tambulig Zamboanga del Sur, Philippines are effective in crime prevention strategies in their capacity as enforcers of the law and to determine whether a relationship exist between crime prevention strategies and crime rate.

METHODS

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive method of research. A thorough investigation and interpretation along with the crime prevention strategies adopted by the police forces in Salug Valley Police Stations was considered in this particular study.

There are three ways a researcher can go about doing a descriptive research project, and they are: (a) Observational, defined as a method of viewing and recording the participants; (b) Case study, defined as an in-depth study of an individual or group of individuals; (c) Survey, defined as a brief interview or discussion with an individual about a specific topic [10].

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 138 active members of the Philippine National Police assigned in the four (4) municipal police stations in Salug Valley, namely: Dumingag Police Station with thirty two (32) active personnel, Mahayag Police Station with thirty nine (39) active personnel, Molave Police Station having forty (40) active personnel and Tambulig Police Station with twenty seven (27) active personnel; one hundred twenty (120) community members (thirty in each municipality) involved in maintenance of Peace and order (School Head, Barangay Officials, leader of private and public sector organization) were utilized in this study

to rate on the effectiveness of the strategies adopted by the PNP in the area. The total number of respondents was subjected for a 5% margin of error. Furthermore, the stratified sampling was used in determining the respondents. Lastly, simple random sampling was utilized in the survey.

Instrument

In essential data gathering, a self-made questionnaire checklist was assembled by the researcher comprising of two parts: Part I contained items for gathering the demographic profile of the respondents. Part II dealt with the effectiveness of the crime prevention strategies of PNP in Salug Valley with six identified variables containing five questions each.

The instrument of the study underwent thorough processes of validation. Contents of the instrument were critically scrutinized by Deans of Criminology Programs in Pagadian and Dipolog City. Revision had been made based on their recommendations and comments.

A draft of the instrument was then presented to the evaluators for comments and suggestions to be incorporated in its revision.

The revised instrument was validated by Chief of Municipal Police Station of Midsalip, Somnot, Ramon Magsaysay and Aurora who verified appropriateness of the questions and recommended to administer the questionnaire.

After which, it was pilot-tested in the town of Aurora which was not covered in this particular investigation. The instrument was reproduced based on the number of police officers assigned in Aurora Police Station and the number of community residents so identified.

Cronbach alpha was used in the computation of data collected during the pilot test. Result of the computed coefficient is 0.87 which is above the accepted level of 0.70 to be reliable.

Lastly, the validated instrument was determined as reliable. The instrument then underwent final revision and printed as to the number of participants, after which it was administered to the participants.

Procedure

Before the instrument was administered to the respondents, the researcher sent a letter requesting the Mayor and chief of Police in each municipality for the approval of the conduct of the study. The letter request contains statement citing the data collected

would be utilized only for research purposes and be treated with utmost confidentiality. Upon approval of the said request, the researcher gathered crime statistics from the record with the assistance of the crime registrar in each station.

As agreed, only index crime was provided to the researcher for confidentiality and secrecy reasons. He went to every municipality and police stations to administer the questionnaire to the respondents asserting openly the purpose of the study and explaining the significance of the information gathered. The researcher assured that anonymity on the responses would be strictly observed to gather honest answer from the respondents. After which, he retrieved the questionnaire personally.

Data Processing Technique

The main statistical tools used in the study were frequency count, rank, percentage, mean computation, Kruskal Wallis Analysis of Variance and simple correlation.

To identify the number of responses belonging to specific category, frequency count was employed.

Mean computation was used to obtain summation of the product of the frequency and the assigned weight divided by the total number of respondents on the perceived level of effectiveness of the crime prevention strategies of PNP Stations in Salug Valley Zamboanga del Sur.

Pearson Correlation was used to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the responses of the community and police officers assigned in different municipal stations along with the variables.

Kruskal-Wallis Analysis of Variance was used to test the difference on the perceived level of effectiveness of crime prevention when grouped by municipality.

T-test was then applied to determine the significant relationship between crime prevention and crime rate in terms of integrated patrol system, barangay peace keeping operations, anti-criminality operations, integrated area community public safety services, bantay turista and school safety project employed by the PNP Stations in Salug valley. After collecting the accomplished form, the researcher tallied all the responses, put into tables for statistical computation as basis for analysis and interpretation of the data.

To draw out the responses on the effectiveness of the crime prevention strategies, the five-point Likert

scale was employed. The criteria which serve as the basis in the interpretation of the results adopted a boundary of number as follows:

Range of Values	Description	Interpretation
4.21- 5.00	Very Much Effective (VME)	Strategies absolutely reduced the crime.
3.41- 4.20	Much Effective (ME)	Strategies mostly reduced the crime.
2.61 – 3.40	Effective (E)	Strategies basically reduced the crime.
1.81 – 2.60	Less Effective (LE)	Strategies fairly reduced the crime.
1.00 – 1.80	Not Effective (NE)	Strategies did not reduced the crime.

For the purpose of objectivity in diagnosing the research problem, the researcher tested the hypothesis at five percent level of significance. If the computed t-value is equal to or greater than the critical t-value at five percent level of significance, the formulated null hypothesis is rejected, likewise if it is lesser in value, null hypothesis is accepted.

Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software was used in the computation. All hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 presents the profile of the police officers in Salug Valley Zamboanga del Sur Philippines as to: Age, Gender and Number of Hours of Training.

Table 1. Profile of PNP officers in Salug Valley

	Profile of PNP Officers	Frequency	Percent
Age:	21 – 25	5	3.62
	26 – 30	38	27.54
	31 – 35	37	26.81
	36 – 40	28	20.29
	41 above	30	21.74
	Total	138	100
Gender:	Male	111	80.43
	Female	27	19.57
	Total	138	100
Number of Hours of Training	20 hours and below	11	7.97
	21 – 30	8	5.8
	31 – 40	4	2.9
	41 – 50	4	2.9
	Above 50 hours	111	80.43
	Total	138	100

Table 1 shows that out of 138 PNP respondents, there were only 5 who belonged to the 21–25 years old bracket; 38 or 27.54 percent belonged to the 26 – 30 years old bracket; 37 or 26.81 percent were 31 – 35 years old; 28 or 20.29 percent were 36 – 40 years old; and 30 or 21.74 percent were above 40 years old. The respondents in general belonged within the age bracket who are already matured and were considered to be knowledgeable in their assignment as law enforcers.

As shown in the table 1, 111 or 80.43 percent of the PNP respondents were males and only 27 or 19.57 percent were females. It could be deduced that the PNP is a male-dominated profession.

This finding is supported with the provision [11] in which the PNP shall organize enlistment procedure prioritizing the recruitment and training of female applicants who shall assigned in the women's desk. In accordance with this necessity, ten percent of its annual recruitment, training, and education quota shall be reserve for women applicants.

Amidst gender concerns, PNP is trying to equate men with women and women with men on their drive on gender equality but females do not give priority to law enforcement profession because of the risky nature of the work associated with it. Women are generally more risk averse than men [12].

A great majority of the PNP personnel have attended trainings of more than 50 hours. Only 4 or 2.90 percent of them have attended training for 31 – 40 hours and 41 – 50 hours; 8 have attended training for 21 – 30 hours and the remaining 11 or 7.97 percent have been trained for less than 20 hours.

This means that PNP are sent to trainings conducted by the PNP headquarters or the equivalent ones. Aside from enrolling in advanced course and taking a master's degree, trainings are also available for PNP personnel especially when there are new assignments or new roles and tasks given to them. Training is very important in order for one to increase productivity among employees.

According to Elnaga and Imran [13] effective training is considered to be a key factor for improved performance; as it can enhance the level of employee and firm competency. It supports to fill the gap between what performance is required and what performance is happening, i.e. gap between desired performance and actual employee performance. Training need referred to any deficit in performance, which can be relieved by appropriate training.

The research has confirmed that training has a big influence on performance with attitude, job satisfaction and service delivery equally getting the same weight. The result is consistent with modern scholars who recommend for training to develop positive attitudes at work place, to increase efficiency and effectiveness in service delivery and improve job satisfaction of the employees [14].

Table 2 presents the overall level of effectiveness of Crime Prevention Strategies of Salug Valley PNP of Zamboanga del Sur Philippines.

Table 2: Level of Effectiveness of Crime Prevention Strategies in Salug Valley

Crime Prevention Strategies	Police		Community	
	AWV	VI	AWV	VI
1. Police integrated Patrol System	3.90	ME	3.98	ME
2. Barangay Peace Keeping Operation	3.92	ME	3.98	ME
3. Anti-Criminality Operations	3.80	ME	3.82	ME
4. Integrated Area Community Public Safety Process	3.98	ME		ME
			4.02	
5. Bantay Turista	3.92	ME	3.95	ME
6. School Safety Project	3.95	ME	3.94	ME
Mean	3.91	ME	3.95	ME

As shown in Table 2, the computed average weighted values and means were within the range of 3.41 – 4.20 which were all described as “Much Effective”. Among the crime prevention strategies implemented in Salug Valley the Integrated Area Community Public Safety Process obtained the highest level of effectiveness above others.

Findings in table 2 point towards crime prevention implemented intensively in the community in order to maintain peace and order in the area. PNP was able to guarantee that there are available personnel on operation all the time ensuring safety in the community and immediate response when there are emergency cases.

Indeed the PNP officers are doing their respective responsibility as far as the conduct of crime prevention programs which greatly contribute in the crime reduction efforts.

Figure 1 and Table 3 show the rate of the index crimes in the Salug Valley Area during the 2nd half of the year 2013 and the first half of the year 2014. As seen on the illustration, physical injury has the highest frequency followed by Theft and Robbery. Murder and Homicide are just few in number together with Cattle Rustling and Carnapping as well as Rape.

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Figure 1. Index Crime Rate in the Salug Valley Area during the second half of the year 2013 and the first half of the year 2014

Table 3. Crime Rate in each Municipality

Index Crimes	Municipalities							
	A		B		C		D	
	X	Y	X	Y	X	Y	X	Y
Murder	5	3	1	1	6	3	10	6
Homicide	5	3	1	0	2	2	3	2
Physical Injury	90	50	42	16	18	28	10	19
Rape	5	0	1	1	0	4	2	7
Theft	44	43	8	5	14	2	6	5
Robbery	20	20	6	1	11	1	3	1
Car napping	4	9	4	1	2	2	2	0
Cattle Rustling	0	2	3	0	0	1	1	1
Percentage Increase	-24.86		-62.12		-18.87		10.81	

Legend:
 X = June – December 2013
 Y = January – June 2014

Figure 1 and Table 3 show the rate of the index crimes in the Salug Valley Area during the 2nd half of the year 2013 and the first half of the year 2014. As seen on the illustration, physical injury has the highest frequency followed by Theft and Robbery. Murder and Homicide are just few in number together with Cattle Rustling and Carnapping as well as Rape.

This goes to show that among the crimes that can possibly be committed by a criminal, Physical Injury is the easiest to commit as well as Theft and Robbery.

Finding on figure 1 and table 3 revealed that for municipalities A, B and C, the crime rates decrease but it was a different scenario for Municipality D where the crime rate increased by more than 10 percent. This means that the crime prevention

strategies were effective in most of the areas but was found to be less effective in another area.

The data suggest that in Salug Valley, people experienced a low crime rate, although crimes were increasing particularly in Municipality of D, it is noteworthy that the crimes are still minimal in numbers compared to other municipalities of Salug Valley.

Table 4. Kruskal-Wallis Test on Police Integrated Patrol System

Municipality	Median	Ave Rank	Z	H-value	P-value
A	4.005	19.2	-0.41	0.83	0.843
B	3.985	23.1	0.81		
C	3.975	20.9	0.11		
D	3.94	18.9	-0.52		

Table 4 shows the Kruskal Wallis Analysis of Variance on the level of effectiveness of crime prevention along Police Integrated Patrol System when grouped by municipality.

The result showed a computed H-value of 0.83 with a p-value of 0.843 which revealed that there is no significant difference on the level of effectiveness of Integrated Patrol System when grouped by municipality. This means that the municipalities have similar level of effectiveness in terms of police integrated patrol system. The effectiveness in one municipality is comparable with that of the others. This could further mean that Police Integrated Patrol System as observed in other municipalities could also be seen in other municipalities within the Salug Valley Area.

Table 5. Kruskal-Wallis Test on Barangay Peacekeeping Operation

Median	Ave Rank	Z	H-value	p-value
3.91	16.0	-1.42	2.54	0.208
3.95	20.8	0.08		
3.91	17.2	-1.03		
4.12	28.1	2.37		

Table 5 shows the test of difference on the level of effectiveness of crime prevention along Barangay Peacekeeping Operations when respondents were grouped by municipality. The result showed a computed H-value of 2.54 with a probability coefficient of 0.208 which means that there is a 20.80 percent probability of acceptance of the null hypothesis. It is then safe to say that there is no

significant difference on the level of effectiveness of crime prevention strategies reflective of Barangay Peacekeeping Operations when respondents were grouped by municipality.

Findings of the study suggest that Barangay Peacekeeping is similarly observable and implemented in all the municipalities of the Salug Valley Area.

Table 6. Kruskal-Wallis Test on Anti-Criminality Operations

Median	Ave Rank	Z	H-value	p-value
3.73	14.9	-1.75		
3.91	25.4	1.51	4.27	0.233
3.775	19.6	-0.28		
3.885	22.2	0.52		

Table 6 presents the test of difference on the level of effectiveness of Anti-Criminality Operations as a crime prevention strategy when respondents were grouped by municipality. The test of difference showed a computed H-value of 4.27 with a p-value of 23.30 percent which leads to the non-rejection of the null hypothesis.

It is then safe to say that there is no significant difference on Anti-Criminality Operations as a crime prevention strategy when respondents were grouped by municipality.

This would mean that the respondents coming from different municipalities have similar ratings which would also redound to the idea that there is similarity in terms of effectiveness of Anti-Criminality Operations strategy done by the PNP personnel in the different municipalities of Salug Valley.

Table 7. Kruskal-Wallis Test on Community Public Safety Services

Municipality	Median	Ave Rank	Z	H-value	p-value
A	4.005	13.4	-2.22	9.74	0.012
B	3.985	16.3	-1.31		
C	3.975	27.0	2.01		
D	3.94	25.4	1.51		

Presented in table 7 is the test of difference on Community Public Safety as a crime prevention strategy when the respondents were grouped by municipality.

The result on the table 7 showed a computed h-value of 9.74 with a probability coefficient of 1.20 percent which showed that there is a difference among the respondents' perception on the level of

effectiveness of the crime prevention strategy by municipality. This may prove that Community Public Safety as an anti-crime prevention strategy is observable at different levels in the different municipalities of the Salug Valley Area.

There may be municipalities that are too safe and there are also municipalities that are generally not safe enough. There are municipalities in which community public safety is not that clear while in some other municipalities, the community people are enjoying the safety and security from the PNP personnel.

Table 8. Kruskal-Wallis Test on Bantay Turista

Municipality	Median	Ave Rank	Z	H-value	p-value
A	3.95	19.1	-0.4	1.28	0.733
B	3.95	20.2	-0.1		
C	3.91	18.7	-0.6		
D	4.0	24.0	1.09		

Shown in table 8 is the test of difference on the level of effectiveness of Bantay Turista as a crime prevention strategy of the PNP. It could be seen on the table 8 that the computed H-value was 1.28 while the percentage of acceptance of the hypothesis is 73.30 percent which means that there is a very high level of acceptability of the hypothesis.

Findings on table 8 revealed that there is no significant difference on the perceived level of effectiveness of Bantay Turista when analyzed by municipality. This means that Bantay Turista as a crime prevention strategy was clearly observable among the municipalities.

Table 9. Kruskal-Wallis Test on School Safety Project

Municipality	Median	Ave Rank	Z	H-value	p-value
A	3.98	18.2	-0.7	1.04	0.791
B	4.0	23.5	0.92		
C	3.95	20.3	-0.1		
D	3.99	20.1	-0.1		

Table 9 shows the test of difference among municipalities as to crime prevention strategies reflective of School Safety Project. The data on the table showed a computed value of 1.04 with a probability value of 79.10 percent which showed very high level of acceptability of the hypothesis. It is then safe to say that there is no significant difference on the level of effectiveness of school safety project when respondents were grouped by municipality.

This means that the level of effectiveness of the crime prevention strategy is almost the same across municipalities in Salug Valley Area. Along this line, it could be said that there is to some degree a sort of comparability of the level of effectiveness of the PNP personnel in the different municipalities.

Table 10. Test of Relationship Between Crime Prevention Strategies and Crime Rate

Variables	r-value	t-value
Crime Prevention	0.361	10.95
Crime Rate	Low Correlation	

Table 10 shows the test of relationship between crime prevention strategies and crime rate. The data on the table showed a computed r-value of 0.361 which is interpreted as low correlation. This means that there is a low correlation between crime prevention strategies and crime rate.

However, when the r-result was subjected to t-test, the resulting value was 10.95 which is greater than the critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between crime prevention and crime rate.

Finding of the study revealed that the crime prevention strategies implemented by the PNP personnel in the municipalities of Salug Valley area is effective and help reduce the occurrence of crime within these municipalities. This would lead to the idea that the crime prevention initiatives were effective in minimizing the crimes. Police visibility, patrolling and other initiatives were done and that it has really helped the community in its drive for peace and order.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Crime prevention strategies adopted by the police forces in Salug Valley Zamboanga del Sur, Philippines was much effective in reducing the crime rate in the area. Crime committed in the area would have been very high if the PNP did not implement these strategies to reduce crime in the four municipalities of Salug Valley.

Younger personnel of the PNP are active and vigorous in their campaign against criminality. The crime prevention strategies of the PNP of Salug Valley are much effective to minimize the crime rate that really helped the community in its drive for peace and order. Partnership of the PNP and the community is the best way to solve criminality. Understanding the

problems within the organization and establishing good rapport with the community will ensure good result.

Assessment by the PNP, School Head, Barangay Officials, leader of private and public sector organization of the four municipalities in Salug Valley Zamboanga del Sur revealed that crime prevention strategies have no significant difference in the level of effectiveness when grouped by municipalities, as a result the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in crime prevention strategies have been accepted in five areas of crime prevention strategies but in Anti-criminality operations the computed result revealed that there is a difference in crime prevention. Furthermore, the hypothesis which states that crime prevention and crime rate have no significant relationship was rejected.

It was found out that, among the four municipalities in the Salug Valley Area, it was in Municipality D where crimes increased. It is highly recommended that the PNP personnel in the area must review their implementation procedures together with the Municipal Peace and Order Council (MPOC) and enhance the strategies by incorporating new approach in dealing with criminality.

Officials of Local Government Unit in Salug Valley, should endeavor to continue their support and cooperation in terms of financial sufficiency, resource management and program implementation on the strategies to augment and maximize the capacity of PNP in crime prevention.

PNP personnel should strengthen the implementation of the different strategies for it to become very much effective in crime prevention. The Chief of Police in each municipality should look into and evaluate the weaknesses of the force with due consideration on the crime strategies adopted by them.

Lastly, future researchers are advised to conduct supplementary research on crime prevention with the aim of discovering new perspective on how to reduce crime occurrence.

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